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Evangelism through Artificial Intelligence Generated-Content: Opportunities and Pitfalls

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Abstract

This paper is an examination of Evangelism through Artificial Intelligence-Generated Content: Opportunities and Pitfalls and in the Global Evangelism: Empowering Believers, Transforming Cultures to replace the human capacity in oblige to the Masters instruction, in an obedience and faithfulness to God's injunctions in Matthew 28:18-20. The paper expounds the compositions of the recipients of God's injunction in Matthew 28:18-20. How it affects the obedience of contemporary disciples in fulfilling the great commission and the task in relation to the Artificial Intelligence-Generated Content in what God has committed in our care. The paper expatiates on the importance of physical presence and roles of human feeling in relation with empathy for the receiver of the gospel message. The study elucidates in brief the historical background of the book of Matthew 28:18-20 with the exegetical work on the message of instructions in the *pericope* to be considering in the fulfilment of it in discipleship. "Go therefore, and make disciples of all nations, baptizing them in the name of the Father, and of the Son, and of the Holy Spirit, teachings them to observe everything that I have commanded you. And see, I am with you always, even to the end of the age," Amen. The paper concludes in respect to follow up in the context with relations to report for the sender-God and reward to the doers-human beings based on the text of Luke 10:17-20.

Keywords: Global Evangelization, Exegesis of Matthew 28:18-20, Disciples and Apostles, Obedient and Faithfulness, Accountability and Reward, Content, Contextualization, Artificial Intelligence, Opportunities and Pitfalls

Introduction

The thesis of this paper is to examine the Evangelism through Artificial Intelligence Generated-Content: Opportunities and Pitfalls. The task is to expounds on Global Evangelism as injunctions of God to all and sundry that have given their life to Christ. Evangelism could be understood as propagating the good news about Jesus Christ, in relation to His death, resurrection, and redemptive work for every mankind from every race, ethnic group, tribe, and even colour. The proclamation of the good news of Christ to the lost souls is the main task of the Church wherever their location in any continent of the globe. The directive of Jesus Christ for all believers in Christ is to propagate the gospel (Matthew 28:19-20). It is an imperative statement. Therefore, evangelism has been an effective instrument by which people encounter the gospel. When people confess Jesus Christ as Lord and Saviour, they are organized together as a local Church in which they could be nurtured, disciple and be baptized according to the injunction of God in Matthew 28:19-20. The work of organizing them requires a deliberate and special skill. Then the gospel must reflect in the lifestyles of the new believers as evidence of the transformed life from dying to a new soul. However, some basic considerations will precede this discuss. Such basics include the etymological considerations of some keywords for the elucidation of the paper in view. The writer of the paper discussed an overview of exegetical text of Matthew 28:18-20 by bringing out the concept of Evangelism in relation with Artificial Intelligence Generated-Content in relations to human capacity in contemporary global evangelization.

Global Evangelization

God delights that all man will be reconciled back to Him; it does not matter how far away they have moved from His love. The love of God prompted Him to send His only begotten Son in the person of Jesus Christ to

the world to reconcile sinful souls back to Himself, which is the great commission. The word “reconciliation” *καταλλαγῆς* is a reference to a way of dealing with and overcoming past alienation and estrangement, enmity and hurt between two parties: a restoration to a forfeited position (Adesanya, 2017). Evangelism is “bringing the whole gospel to the whole man,” it is the ministry of the Church. This is known as the heartbeat of God (Hustard, 1993). The cost of this reconciliation was the death of Jesus Christ who came to the world and shed His blood on the cross, where He exclaimed, “it is finished” in thousands of years ago to save the souls of the sinners, which is the intention of God. Evangelism is the main task of a local Church and every gender and children must not be left out of receiving the gospel and sharing the same gospel.

The term “Gospel” literally means “good news” or “proclaiming good news” (Brand, et. al, 2003). The English word “gospel” is from the Greek word *εὐαγγέλιον* (Anthony, 2001), which means “good, merry, glad, and joyful tidings (Mounce, 2001) or good news (Anthony, 2001). “Gospel,” is the good tidings of the kingdom of God and salvation through Christ, to be received by faith on the basis of His expiatory death, His burial, resurrection, and ascension (Vine, 1939). Then the gospel was committed to the care of the Lord’s disciple who later became an apostles and leader of the Church universal as to make “disciples” of all the nations, tribes, races and gender to the saving knowledge of God (Acts. 1:8). This word appears seventy-five times in the New Testament as “good news” (Mounce, 2001), which shows how important the gospel is, especially when it is directed to an unregenerate soul.

In the Old Testament texts, the Hebrew terms for Evangelism are *besorah* (noun) and *basar* (verb), which the *Septuagints* translates into Greek as *εὐαγγελιον* and *εὐαγγελιζω* respectively. These terms refer to the activity of culminating significant news in any general sense (1 Samuel 4:17; 1 Kings 1:42). But they come to mean significant news in a specific sense-God’s acts of salvation, most importantly the promised eschatological salvation of His people (Psalms 40:9 96:2; Isaiah 40:9, 41:27 61:1 and Nahum 1:15), (Douglas, 1996). Therefore, there is need for individuals to be empowered with correct contents of the Master’s guide, He even promised to be with us (Matthew 28:20b) and then by the time our mouth is opened for the proclamation, He will definitely fill us with the right and appropriate contents of Words from the Scripture (Psalms 81:10).

Disciples and Apostles for Evangelization

The Discipleship can be defined as the process of being a follower, learner, and adherent of Jesus. It connotes a person who follows Jesus as Master, teacher, and Lord (Matt. 7:28-29; 8:25; Luke 8:24). Discipleship is the process by which a believer learns to live like Christ, think like Christ, and serve like Christ. The term disciple is derived from the Greek word “μαθητής,” which gives the stem expression of a ‘student,’ ‘pupil,’ ‘follower,’ ‘adherent’ or ‘disciple’ that is closely linked to a *διδάσκαλος*,” which is translated as a ‘religious leader,’ ‘master’ or ‘teacher.’ The concept of a disciple gained dominance during the time of Jesus and his followers (Wilkins, 1992).

Apostle: The word Apostle comes from the Greek word and it is used in the gospels to designate the twelve disciples called and sent out to preach of the kingdom and demonstrate the presence of God. The term is not applied to Jesus Himself in the gospel, nevertheless that the thought of himself as the apostle of God (Kruse, 1992). The Greek word “ἀπόστολος,” was used only frequently in the Greek language prior to the New Testament times.

In classical Greek, “ἀπόστολος,” was used in an impersonal way, for example, it was used in reference to the dispatch of a fleet or an army and then in reference to the fleet itself. The use of the term “ἀπόστολος,” in the gospels and indeed its powerful usage throughout the New Testament is a designation for someone who is sent by Christ to convey a message from God (Barnett, 1993). In the words of Morris Ashcraft, “Anyone who would understand the Christian ministry must not only define the term but must also show what the concepts were embedded in its usage and what it meant to those who claimed to be apostles” (Ashcraft, 1958)

even in relation to Evangelism. The writer is of opinion that whoever, that propounded a concept must actually share in the experience of the identity for others to learn and follow succinctly. This will lead to the contents for the evangelism.

Contents for the Evangelization

Contents of the message in Evangelism is very crucial and important for the purposes of soul winning and spreading the gospel of our Lord Jesus Christ. The content of Global Evangelism is the use of words and Word. The words here is the verbal communication explore for the propagation of the Gospel to yet unreachable souls around our local and global environ. Then the Word is the use of the name of Jesus Christ, Who is the Subject of the discussion to everyone that comes our ways. In the name of the Lord Jesus Christ, the Saviour of the whole world. Who died for our sin, because without the shedding of the blood there is no remission of sins (Hebrews 9:22). In addition to that content is gospel to preach, which should be center on Jesus Christ Crucifixion with the truth about Christ death and resurrection for sin. Then the preacher should explore the content of allowing an individual for an invitation to repent and believe in Christ. Therefore, for an evangelism to be fulfill in consonant with the injunction of the Master-Jesus, these contents should be applied in an evangelization.

Contextualization of Global Evangelization

The concept of contextualization dates back to the first century Christianity. The expressions of Paul the Apostle in one of his letters to the Corinthians Christians are regarded as biblical basis for contextualization. Paul wrote:

and unto the Jews I became as a Jew that I might gain the Jews; to them that are under the law as under the law that I might gain them that area under the law; To them that are without the law as without law... that I might gain them that are without the law. To the weak became I as weak that I might gain the weak, that I might by all means save some (1 Corinthians 9:21-22).

Contextualization has a focus always. Since its usage in 1972, through the courtesy of the Theological Education Fund when it published *Ministry in Context. The Third Mandate of the Theological Education fund* (Hesselgrave and Rommen 1989). Several authors have contributed to the discussion on the contextualization. Contextualization is the process of interpreting Christian truth in terms of applying it to the real-life issue arising from the sociocultural context within which the interpreters live (Akande, 2012).

Contextualization is defined as "the translation of the unchanging context of the Gospel of the Kingdom into verbal form, meaningful to the people in their separate cultures and within their particular existential situation. This was defined by Nicholls B. J. and Peter, G. W., whom they identified with, the thoughts of Kraft in their definition of Contextualization, cited by (Hesselgrave and Rommen 1989). The main key word in Kraft's thought is "interpretation" whereas Nicholls and Peter engaged the term "translation." It was observed that the task of Contextualization in Evangelism transcends "translation" (Ishola, 1993), for the same reason the idea of "interpretation" in the definition of Kraft will make the writer prefer another definition because "interpretation" is not all that is there to Contextualization in Evangelism.

Contextualization is "the attempt to communicate the message of the person, works, word and will of God in a way that is faithful to God's revelation especially as it is put forth in the teachings of Holy Scripture and that is meaningful to respondents in their respective cultural and existential contexts (Hesselgrave and Rommen, 1989) for an Evangelism. The writer then subscribes and oblige to the definition of Hesselgrave and Rommens clear and inclusive for the purpose of this paper and thus adopts it. It reflects the contents of an Evangelization for a global purpose.

Exegesis of Matthew 28:18-20

Background to the Book of Matthew

The authorship of the book of Matthew is acceptable by Christian and no one has seriously questioned that he wrote the book that bears his name. Matthew was an early disciple, leaving his post as tax collector in Capernaum to follow Jesus Christ. Later he was chosen as one of the twelve apostles. Many think that as tax collector, he was compulsive in taking notes as he surveyed the caravans and travellers who passed through his tax table. Matthew took notes on Jesus' sermons and wrote down the miracles that He performed.

Many feel that Matthew was the first of the books written in the New Testament, and was therefore placed first in order. Only a few people think that he wrote at a later date, between A.D. 58-68 (Townes, 2003). It is obvious that Matthew did write before the destruction of the Jewish temple, because his writing included the prediction that the temple would be destroyed (Matthew 24-25). Apparently, the temple was still standing when he wrote. The key word is *king*, and Matthew attempts to demonstrate that Jesus fulfils the prophecies of Messiah, the coming King (Townes, 2003).

The vast majority expounds and analyses the subject from the standpoint of normative Christian theology: what the Bible says, what Christian mission requires and how it should be implemented - in short, what Christians ought to do about it and how Christians ought to obey Christ's Great Commission in Matthew 28:18-20 (Fanning, 2011). The focus of this is to exegete the text, which would help us to expatiate and arrive at the summations that there is Opportunities and Pitfalls through Artificial Intelligence Generated-Content for Evangelism.

The Theological Context of Matthew 28:18-20

This passage plays a vital role as a motif for Clarion call for Christian gathering, causing people to recall the significance of mission and evangelism. In fact, this passage functions as a support - even a command - allowing Christians to legitimize almost every kind of missionary work in order to compel non-Christians to become disciples of Jesus (Chung, 2015). Matthew uses five lines to present this scenario. He first covers the characters and setting, then he moves on to the circumstances around the context. He gives them motivation for their action, commands them, which is an imperative on what to do and how to do it, and finally, closes with a promise that only God can make disciples (Phelps 2011).

Therefore, Jesus commissions the disciples to go out and make disciples of all the nations by creating communities of obedience among the nations. 'Mission is replicated discipleship, learned through ethical obedience and passed on through teaching' (White & Assimeng, 2017). This text in consideration Matthew 28:18-20 is the pivotal foundation on global evangelism, which is transferable to another generations. Therefore, to make a disciples is an imperative and a prerogative of God's intention to cause increase and expansion of His kingdom on earth. This could be achievable through man's obedient and faithfulness to the Caller and Master-Jesus.

The Text Matthew 28:18-20

Verse 18 The Use of "All Authority" (*ἐξουσία*)

In Matthew 28:18-20, the one who spoke on the commission is the one who had been given (*ἐξουσία*) "all authority" (v. 18) to do so. The authority of Christ is not a new theme in this gospel (Mt 7:29; 10:1, 7-8; 11:27; 22:43-44; 24:35). His power to overcome the devil (Mt 4:1-11), to teach like no other (7:28-29), to calm nature (8:23-27), to forgive sin (9:1-8) and to heal the sick (9:27-31) had already been established (Lawless, 2011). Thus, Authority refers to the power of deity assumed by Him at His resurrection and ascension. Authority in this text is transferred to believers in Christ, because, regarding His divine nature, "all power" has been always His portion of. Jesus approaches disciple before the commission in verse 19, he assures them of his sovereignty over heaven and earth. Christ addresses His disciples - some of whom are hesitant to worship

Him - and clearly expresses His exalted position of authority. Matthew 28:18b expresses Jesus' consciousness of full authority with a view to wielding that authority in the command that follows (Chung, 2015). Then Jesus claims universal authority. It is on the basis of this mediatorial authority, in heaven and on earth, that the Saviour issues His commission to His followers' (Thomas, 2000). The writer put succinctly that, because, He was sent by His Father. He counted on the authority of His Father to control all the circumstances and resources, which is to enable Him to carry out His mission, also He expects His disciples to count on His authority to fulfil and obey all his commands as He did in obedience to the Father's will.

The indicative statement that introduces the Great Commission ('all authority in heaven and on earth has been given to me') alerts us to the reality that Jesus is not only a teacher - he is the Lord. Jesus indicates that the resurrection was His enthronement, the beginning of His kingly reign, when He says, "All authority in heaven and on earth has been given to me". Authority, indicating Matthew's Christological theme, which translated from the Greek word ἐξουσία "power or right". By proclaiming Himself as the highest and only authority, Jesus Himself stands behind the command of verse 19 (Hertig, 2001). The command to make disciples is related to the claim of authority through use of the conjunction οὖν (Lee & Viljoen, 2010). The gospel points to Jesus as the final, ultimate and complete revelation of God, but this arrangement is then punctuated by Jesus' own words: All authority is given to Me in heaven and earth'. This passage can, with good reason, refer to Jesus in almost Pauline terms as the one in whom heaven and earth have their completion - the new Adam in which God establishes His new creation (Col 1:15-16). God establishes Christ as the new Adam, the man from heaven (1 Cor. 15:45) in whom His new humanity is joined together - not by blood, but by the proclamation of the gospel, baptism and faith (Scaer, 1991). What is more important for this paper is that this authority is given in heaven and on earth. It is a universal authority. Jesus is assuring His disciples that there is no other power in heaven or on earth than the power that the Father has given Him, which is also endowing the disciples and other believers in Christ.

Verse 19 The Use of "all the nations,"

The phrase *all the nations* (πάντα τὰ ἔθνη) points to the unrestricted nature of mission for Evangelism. The Great Commission's phrase πάντα τὰ ἔθνη must include every human, because it includes the qualifying adjective πάντα [all] as narrative of the sheep and goats. In fact, Evangelism (mission) to the Jews had already been commanded (Mt 10:6) and is now taken for granted (25:32). Furthermore, it would be absurd to imagine that a mission mandate given from a Jew to Jewish disciples would exclude Jews, especially when they have already been included (Mt 10:6; Hertig, 2001). Some understand the term ἔθνη as referring only to Gentiles - an interpretation likely built on a belief that God had ultimately rejected the Jews who had first rejected Him (Lawless, 2011). Others view 'nations' as 'peoples' or 'ethnic groups'. Gentiles and Jews alike would thus have been included in this call. The gospel is for all the world - not only for the lost sheep of Israel (Lawless, 2011).

The word *nations* translates from the word ἔθνη from which we have the English word *ethnic*. Today we use the expression *ethnic people group* to define the many ethno-linguistic distinct groups of people that consider themselves different from other people because of their unique language, culture and beliefs. (Fanning, 2011). Most scholars, accept the view that πάντα τὰ ἔθνη should be translated as 'all the nations' which includes both the Jews and the Gentiles. On this reading of the text, the original mission to the Jews is now expanded to include the Gentiles. It emphasizes the importance of Jesus' focus on all nations according to (Sim, 2014). This marks a shift from Jesus as a Jewish rabbi to Jesus as the way to redeem the entire world. If the disciples can change the people of all nations, the world can be redeemed (Hiebert, 1992). What is important and even shocking for Matthew's Jewish audience is that the new followers of Jesus are to come from the Gentiles and that they, the descendants of the patriarchs, have lost their special status (Mt 8:11-12).

Jesus had given command to his disciples to go to the lost sheep of the house of Israel. It is noteworthy that ethnic is a neuter plural, and would thus be expected as the proper form in opposition to it (Scaer, 1991). Therefore, it is better to take the commission here as expanding the 'mission' of Matthew 10:5 to include all ethnic groups. What Matthew intends with this reading, is that the disciples understand that their mission is to ethnic groups and they must preserve the ethnic identity of each group. Group conversions can, and perhaps should be the norm. Thus, Jesus commands the making of disciples of individuals from all ethnic groups, including Judaism (Freeman, 1997). The mandate is that Christians have to proclaim the good news to all nations and thus fulfil the commission given by Christ in verse 19 (Tucker & Woodbridge, 2012). Jesus commissioned the disciples and apostles to a worldwide Evangelism, which was parallel and in contrast to Rome's desire for worldwide societal control (Cronshaw, 2016). This benefit of welfare would then explain why the mission command contains an injunction to baptize all nations and to bring new believers in through a confirmation of the triune God working cohesively (Chung, 2015). The task is for all.

Verse 20 The Use of the expression "Teach all Things"

The command is to 'teach all things,' and the author records Jesus giving a command for active evangelism in those discourses. Then the command would apply to believers at all times and in all places because of Christ's command in Matthew 28 (Phelps, 2011). The final phrase of the Great Commission, 'teaching them to obey everything that I have commanded', refers to the on-going training in all the commands of the New Testament. The phrase *to obey* means 'to attend to carefully, or to guard a prisoner'. It refers to a lifestyle of learning, remembering and practicing all the teaching commands of Jesus and the Holy Spirit throughout the New Testament (Fanning, 2011).

Obedience to the Master is paramount on the both side of the disciples and the recipients of the gospel. Therefore, for an individual to be able to receive a reward from the Lord Jesus Christ, such person must fulfil the mandate. Teaching them to obey everything I have commanded you' provides the content of what is to be passed on to others in the process of discipleship and apostleship. If the disciples are to teach them to obey 'everything' Jesus has commanded, then the mission and evangelization of the disciples is to be holistic (Hertig, 2001). Discipleship and Apostleship involves diligent teaching of the gospel and practices that promotes a lifestyle of becoming ever more like Jesus Christ. Discipleship is not limited to what you can comprehend - it must transcend all understanding. It is a life of strict adherence and obedience, faithfulness and accountability to Christ and His commandments also adherence to Christ as the object of our faith (White & Assimeng, 2017). To teach is a means of evangelization in part of the world. This requires diligence and commitment perpetually.

The 'teaching' of verse 20 refers to the communication of the total revelation and good news, which God has given in Jesus and not only the call to faith. The call to repentance (i.e. contrition and faith) is the call to be baptized. The teaching (*διδάσκοντες*) goes beyond that call. The disciples and apostles are sent to teach the new disciples to keep what Jesus commanded. It is Jesus' own teaching and not the Torah that is the substance of what is to be taught. Throughout Matthew, the emphasis has been on Jesus as the teacher. Now the disciples are for the first time commissioned to also teach. However, it is not just that they are to teach. They are to teach the converts 'to keep' (*τηρεῖν*) that which Jesus taught. This verb adds a distinctively ethical dimension to the teaching. Christianity is Torah-based, but it is, nevertheless, inherently moral. Any proclamation of the gospel, which does not have this Christocentric ethic, is not the gospel as Matthew presents it (Freeman, 1997).

Thus, the disciples are commanded to baptize those who believe and after the baptism to orientate the believers in the way that they should live here on earth as the children of God. This commandment is based on the whole gospel of Jesus without selecting some facts. It means the gospel of Jesus, as presented in the Great Commission, is a holistic gospel. It has an ability to cover various areas of life as Jesus taught his

disciples. The Great Commission is a command to teach the believers the whole truth without compromise; it is teaching without fear and favour.

In verse 20: The Use of "the Promise" 'I am with you always, even to the end of the ages'

The promise of Jesus at the end of Matthew, 'I am with you always, even to the end of the ages' (v.20), was much more than a perfunctory closing to a call statement. It was an announcement of victory even in the midst of persecution. In all of these dangerous situations, the disciples would need to trust the bookend truths of Matthew's Gospel: the virgin-born redeemer, named 'God with us' (1:27) would be with them to the end (28:20; Lawless 2011). That suggest the assurance of His presence and provision is already available for such disciples as individual embark on evangelism.

This last promise in Matthew extends beyond the life span of the disciples to every believer that commits to the task of raising up a group of Christ-followers among every ethno-linguistic group of people on earth 'to the end of the age' (v. 20b). This phrase is found in Matthew 13:39-40, 49; 24:3 which refers to the end of the present age when the Son of Man returns to establish his kingdom. Thus, the promise not only applied to these first century disciples, but to every disciple since then and until the end of the church age (Fanning, 2011). The responsibility ends with the promise of Jesus' presence, protection and provision, which is similar to those Old Testament passages in which God promised His presence always to those He sent out.

Now they are promise that He will be with them all the days until the consummation of the ages. In Matthew 1:23 the name *Immanuel* was interpreted as 'God (is) with us'. Now the disciples are assure that, as they go in his name, he will continue to be Immanuel to them. This suggest to us that, provision of the materials and contents is readily available with the Immanuel for our needs and consumptions. He is Spirit and those will serve Him must be in Spirit so as receive an inspiration from Him and not a generated-content from Artificial Intelligence for purpose of the Global Evangelism.

Obedience and Faithfulness towards Evangelization

The hallmark of the call to discipleship and apostleship is to be obedient and faithful to the assignment and commission that our Master has committed to our hands. Obedience is a basic aspect of the believers in Christ's faith, and comprehending its true definition can deepen our relationship with God's guide and guard our daily lives. Furthermore, Obedience is defined by hearing, listening, and responding to God with reverence and assent. In line with the Hebrew traditions signifies subordination and hearing under authority of Christ, while in Greek, it implies persuasion and acting on what is heard. It is a test of faith and reverence for God, on a condition for a right relationship with Him. Obedience to God's imperative is an act of worship and an expression of love for Jesus Christ. It enhances commitment to clarion call on Global Evangelism in accordance with the great commission. Our faithfulness is required in order to be able to fulfil the task of evangelizing within the community and outside individual domain. Obedience aligns with a command from one's superior or deity. Jesus gave a command to all His disciple so as to be faithful to the work of spreading the good news about the Lord Jesus Christ. Instructions to be adhere to is given by the Lord Jesus Christ to those whom He sent for evangelizing and this requires accountability.

Accountability and Reward for Evangelization

God is the rewarder of those who diligently seek and serve Him. Whenever the saviour comes, He will reward everyone according to obedience and faithfulness. This is in the prerogative of the Lord. According to the text, Luke 10:17-20, the disciples came and give report of their encounter and outcome of experience when they did go for evangelism. The accountability of man depends on individual diligence and obedience to only what you are told to do, is what the Lord will use to reward His disciples and apostles.

Whoever that fulfil the mandate of the Master to His desire shall be surely rewarded, which place subsume to obedience to the faithfulness to the call of the Master, as regard to the great commission is applied to. Jesus says “And, behold, I come quickly; and my reward is with me, “to give every man according as his work shall be” (Revelation 22:12).

To be rewarded for the work done, it shows that God is faithful to His promise. Whether our Evangelism generated-content is through Artificial Intelligence or from study the manuscripts directly, the Lord will surely rewards obedience and faithfulness to His standard. Paul says that *I am allowed to anything- but not everything is good for you. You say, “I am allowed to do anything - but not everything is beneficial (1 Cor. 10:23, NLT).* Whichever individual prefer must be what is leading to a point in time for the inspirational for the fulfilment of His purpose and counsel in a particular life for His glory alone also be rewarded for it from our Saviour should be our priority.

Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Artificial Intelligence plays a vital role in Generated-Content for Global Evangelism with evolving of sophisticated technologies advancement being deployed to pursue evangelism in the 21st century.

In addition, Artificial Intelligence could not replace human capacity in the spreading of the good news to domain of the recipients of the gospel in this dispensation rather it will improve the accessibility to quality resource material through the use of digital technologies and irrespective of time and locations. The term Artificial Intelligence known as Artificial Intelligence appeared for the first time in 1956 at a small conference at Dartmouth College, New Hampshire (Adebayo & Atowoju, 2024). Since then, lots of discipline in many fields such as Computer Sciences or even philosophy are still arguing about what an Artificial Intelligence is.

John McCarthy, initially coined the term, Artificial Intelligence. In 1956 when he invited a bunch of researchers from a variety of disciplines as well as language simulation, vegetative cell nets, quality theory, and a lot of, to a summer workshop known as the Dartmouth Summer Research on Artificial Intelligence to debate about what would ultimately become the sphere of Artificial Intelligence (Kaplin and Haenlein, 2019), which was culled from the article of (Adebayo & Awotoju, 2024). An Artificial Intelligence is a computer program or a robot that can learn and improve to solve problems as usually done by humans or an intelligent subject. Artificial Intelligence is a computer system able to perform tasks that normally require human intelligence, such as visual perception, speech recognition, decision-making, and translation between languages (Redmond, 2011). Not only that, sourcing for the vocabulary in relation to different fields of endeavours and correct text of Scripture for the Evangelization in an Intercultural setting in a global context. Artificial Intelligence has swiftly established itself as a revolutionary force in a vast variety of organizations, including religious settings (Adebayo & Atowoju, 2024). The evolution of Artificial Intelligence has resulted in an array of development and innovations that have impacted Spiritual aspect of human life. Life is in two coins, likewise in the all facets of life endeavours even religious and evangelism is not being left out, that is why as the opportunities emerges and so is the pitfalls.

Opportunities of Artificial Intelligence Generated-Content on Global Evangelism

Artificial Intelligence Generated-Content can offer various opportunities for evangelism in the midst of global context such as: *Creating Content in Multiple Language and Collaborations*

Artificial Intelligence tools can facilitate collaboration among evangelists by providing suggestions, insights, and feedback on academic papers, leading to higher-quality content and ideas. AI can help you translate your content into multiple languages, expanding your global outreach and reaching more people. However, it is essential to consider cultural and linguistic nuances to ensure the content is accurate and culturally sensitive. Human editing and oversight are crucial in this process to ensure that the translated content

effectively conveys the intended message and values of the church. With the help of Artificial Intelligence, one can break down language barriers and share your message with a broader audience.

Enhances the Preachers Intellectual Experience and Optimizations

Thanks to its sophisticated tool-set and the ability to analyze texts of the Scripture as an Artificial Intelligence. Artificial Intelligence will improve the preacher intellectual capacity about his service in the commission and task of Evangelism. Doing so allows the preacher to adapt their tools of the text and services to current and future Gospel spreads. Artificial Intelligence solutions aim to enable the highest level of efficiency and enhance the preacher intellectual experience with the competence in the workforce by foretelling the works and the word of God for the tasks of the Gospel to be fulfilled.

To Avoid Human Error in Biblical Analysis

Artificial Intelligence can never be entirely error-free. However, the more data provides our algorithms – and the better technologies individuals use – the better our Artificial Intelligence-based tools can perform. That means faster execution of tasks with more accurate results than if individual is asked to do the same activities. And in many cases, the accuracy is close to One hundred percent. Artificial intelligence is less susceptible to errors than people because it does not suffer from human characteristics like fatigue and distraction. It works effectively, no matter the time of day, avoiding emotions, opinions, and prejudice – only ever making objective decisions.

To Generate more Meaningful Biblical Insights

Artificial Intelligence analytical capabilities can put someone in a position of serious strength. Robust exegetical analysis allows for better biblical insight with a result, more reliable insights into emerging trend of theological discuss on evangelism and its concept in 21st century. Interestingly, Artificial Intelligence can even predict behavioural context of the Biblical time, which illustrates how it can be of help to approach any context in our time (Majewski, et al. 2024).

To Save Time and Cost

Artificial Intelligence can help by automating long, repetitive tasks so as to save time-frame. Before embarking on the evangelism, there is a provision for empowering the people by counseling and teaching them on how to share the gospel in relation to the peculiarity of the individual's believe and Intercultural millieu. Jesus says, *'We must quickly carry out the tasks assigned us by the one who sent us. The night is coming, and then no one can work, (John 9:4 NLT)*. Using machine learning and neural networks for a seminar about a particular environment individual creates, then deploys a tool that can reduce the time taken on the task.

Improve Systematic Presentation and Choice of Words for Proclamations

Artificial Intelligence has resulted in better data strategies. In truth, it has had an unprecedented impact systematic and choice of word performance in short, AI can Improve gospel presentation through media focused and create more relevant and engaging content to target a broader audience and create more effective proclamations. Additionally, AI can enable the development of autonomous lifestyles, and enhance educational experiences and development through personalized learning. Overall, the possibilities with Artificial Intelligence are vast and continue to expand as technology advances.

Pitfalls of Artificial Intelligence Generated-Content on Global Evangelism

Lack of Inspirational and Guidance of the Holy Spirit

In the book of John 14:26, "there is a promise of the comforter who will teach you all things" now that AI is to generate-content for evangelism, there is place of Holy Spirit inspiring the disciples again. It shows it is now by machine efforts not by His Spirit any longer. But individual disciple and apostle supposes to depend on God. Zechariah says, so he said to me, "This is the word of the LORD to Zerubbabel: "Not by might nor by power, but by my Spirit," says the LORD Almighty. " (Zechariah 4:6).

Lack of Originality and Creativity

It is known that large language models produce content based on the patterns and information they have been trained on. In other words, the resulting content may mirror common themes, phrases, and ideas found in its training information. It often leads to repetitive, formulaic and generic contents. Then, if two separate individuals wrote on the same prompt, an AI tool will share similar thought or idea, with some minor changes in the content delivery. Sharing thought of generated-content, it would not need go in out any longer, in as much individual can access the AI then it reduces the original content of direct inspiration from God who sent the disciples. Therefore, no fresh perspective in the way of doing things even regarding spreading of the good news.

Lack of Personal Expressions

An AI generated-content comes in "templates," whereas individual disciples have personalities, distinct tones, and perspectives. This allows us to resonate better with readers and create a strong connection and empathy with the listener in our context. Generative contents lack their own personal expressions because they create content based on patterns, data, and information gather and analyzed rather than personal expressions or unique styles.

Lack of Ethical Issues

Moreover, AI writing tools may reinforce harmful stereotypes or infringe on intellectual property rights. Engaging in such practices may damage individual reputation, such an individual not the content creator and in the midst of academia known as plagiarism and where in the spiritual palace, is known as "Lukewarmness." Which is what God hates and there is no reward for such an individual after all the labour for the Master.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Evangelism through Artificial Intelligence Generated-Content should be thoroughly screened and injects one's personal ideas and inspiration through the guidance of the Holy Spirit. Even whenever individuals, source for an idea, Bible references, and otherwise, the originality should not be left out. Because it is the Spirit individual disciple is addressing and not a machine without the Spirit of God. In doing these aforementioned above it would reduce the pitfalls to the barest minimum, in that AI generated-content that will minister to a soul. In the word of the Paul the Apostle, "For we wrestle not against flesh and blood, but against rulers, against powers, against the princes of the darkness of this world, against spiritual wickedness in the heavenly places" (Eph. 6:12). God will help us to be able to fulfil our mandate on the "great commission," that is Evangelism.

Recommendations

1. The paper recommends a synergy between the department of Religious and Intercultural studies to adopt a media and Internet unit that will propose a Biblical and Theologically base references for the

uploading online for Artificial Intelligence generated-content sourced for, from a contextualized perspective in our own region for evangelism.

2. The Nigerian Association of Pastoral Counsellors (NAPCOUN) should organize a seminar to her members and those interested on how to extract needed information from an online Artificial Intelligence and allow to make a personal expression to the AI generated-content to be adopted or use for global evangelism.
3. Let everyone to be conscious of the fact that our calling into evangelism is God's imperative and He is willing to supply everything needed for the propagation of the good news for His glory alone and understand that He is coming soon to reward everyone that are obedient and faithful their responsibility.
4. Artificial Intelligence generated-content should not be to totally dependent on because like what happened to internet globally and delayed services in some banking hall that day and individual should be originality of His content to be used for evangelism. Individual should be a content generator for the evangelism.

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